

seedborne rice fungi.

pH level. Infection percentages were higher at substrate moisture at pH 5-6.

Type of container. Higher infection percentages were detected in semitransparent plastic petri dishes than in glass petri dishes.

Use of streptomycin. When 100 ppm concentration streptomycin solution was used as substrate moisture, higher infection of *D. oryzae*, *T. padwickii*, and *Phoma* spp. could be detected, but growth and detection of *P. oryzae* were

reduced.

2,4-D. Use of low concentrations 2,4-D (0.05%–0.10%) in the substrate moisture restricted root growth and facilitated detection of most of the important fungi. □

Table 1. Effect of incubation temperature on infection percentage of seedborne rice pathogens by blotter method. Imphal Pin, India.

Temperature (°C)	Infection detected (%)									
	<i>D. oryzae</i>	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>T. padwickii</i>	<i>N. oryzae</i>	<i>Curvularia</i> spp.	<i>Alternaria</i> spp.	<i>Phoma</i> spp.	<i>Fusarium dimerum</i>	<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	
17	13	8	16	12	21	2	9	11	2	
22	18	22	16	16	20	6	10	18	4	
27	18	15	20	13	21	4	10	15	2	
32	19	5	27	11	27	1	10	17	0	
CD (0.05)	4	4	4	3	5	3	ns	3	2	

Table 2. Effect of light on infection percentages of seedborne rice pathogens. Imphal Pin, India.

Light h/d	Mean infection percentage transformed into angles ^a									
	<i>D. oryzae</i>	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>T. padwickii</i>	<i>N. oryzae</i>	<i>Curvularia</i> spp.	<i>Alternaria</i> spp.	<i>Phoma</i> spp.	<i>F. sernitectum</i>	<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	
0 (24 h darkness)	15.83 (7.44)	12.91 (5.0)	14.86 (6.57)	24.17	28.34 (22.53)	22.62	18.76	6.99	13.46	
4	22.38 (14.50)	16.66 (8.22)	21.26 (13.15)	26.76	33.25 (30.07)	24.03	21.06	7.60	13.45	
8	23.42 (15.80)	20.04 (11.74)	24.38 (17.04)	27.35	33.59 (30.61)	25.57	21.48	8.24	11.19	
12	24.69 (17.45)	22.68 (14.86)	26.17 (19.45)	27.66	35.73 (34.00)	27.13	21.25	8.69	11.32	
16	25.36 (18.34)	21.57 (13.51)	26.78 (20.30)	27.17	34.72 (32.43)	25.85	21.83	13.66	11.43	
20	23.75 (16.25)	21.34 (13.24)	25.66 (18.75)	27.47	33.23 (30.03)	26.46	21.60	11.91	12.83	
CD (0.05)	3.50	3.32	6.39	ns	3.81	ns	ns	ns	ns	

^aFigures in parentheses indicate values transformed back to percentages.

Cost comparison of neem oil and an insecticide against rice tungro virus (RTV)

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The potential of neem oil (NO) mixed with custard-apple oil (CAO) was evaluated in three consecutive croppings 1984-85. A 50% NO:CAO mixture in 4:1 proportion at 8 liters/ha was sprayed with an ultralow volume (ULV) applicator at weekly intervals from seedling to maximum tillering stages. The treated control was sprayed with BPMC at 0.75 kg ai/ha and the untreated control with 1.66% Teepol-water solution (emulsifier). Incidence of

Comparative RTV control, yield, and net gain in ricefields sprayed with neem oil and insecticide.^a IIRRI, 1987.

Treatment	RTV (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Value of yield (\$)	cost of treatment (\$)	Net gain (value of yield less cost of treatment ^b)
<i>Jan-Apr 1984</i>					
NO:CAO	5 a	6.1 a	1068	44	1024
BPMC	4 a	6.1 a	1068	125	943
Control	7 a	5.6 a	980	12	968
<i>Jun-Oct 1984</i>					
NO:CAO	4 a	5.1 a	892	44	848
BPMC	6 ab	4.7 a	822	125	697
Control	9 b	4.6 a	805	12	793
<i>Nov 1984-Mar 1985</i>					
NO:CAO	29 a	3.1 a	542	44	498
BPMC	56 b	2.5 b	438	125	313
Control	52 b	2.3 b	402	12	390

^aAv of 4 replications/cropping season. Cost of palay = US\$0.175/kg (NFA price). NO:CAO mixture and BPMC were applied 8 times during each cropping season. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bCost of treatment includes labor and materials. Control treatment cost included labor (US\$10) and 8 pc DC batteries (US\$2) for applying 1.66% Teepol-water solution (emulsifier) using an ULV-spray applicator.

RTV and yield are shown in the table.

Jan-Apr 1984, RTV incidence was negligible and yields were high in all treatments. Jun-Oct 1985, plots treated with the oil mixture had significantly less RTV infection than the untreated

control (9% RTV), but yields were not significantly different. Nov 1984-Mar 1985, RTV incidence was significantly less in plots treated with the oil mixture than in insecticide-treated and untreated control plots. Yield was significantly

higher in plots treated with the oil mixture.

Net gain was consistently higher in plots treated with NO:CAO than in untreated or insecticide-treated plots. □

Ufra threatens deepwater rice in Majuli, Assam

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Ufra disease caused by stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* was severe in deepwater rice on Majuli, the river island of Brahmaputra in Assam. About 2,000 ha was badly damaged. Symptoms observed included the characteristic white patches of barren rice plants, panicles of many plants that did not emerge, or only half emerged, and stems of many plants that produced aborted skeletons of deformed panicles (see

Aborted panicles of rice due to stem nematode. Assam, India.

figure). Variety Padmapani appeared to escape the disease, probably because of

its early maturity (Nov). Popular variety Rangabao was severely affected.

Ufra problem in low-lying areas of Bangladesh

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We surveyed the disease situation of five low-lying areas during the 1986 aman (Apr-Dec). Three zones in the south, where ricefields are subjected to tidal submergence twice every 24 h, were found to be ufra prone (see figure).

Tidal water helps spread ufra

Outbreak of ufra disease in Bangladesh.